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HEMIJA I ZAŠTITA
ŽIVOTNE SREDINE

ENVIROCHEM2023

*9th SYMPOSIUM
CHEMISTRY AND ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION*

ENVIROCHEM2023

KNJIGA IZVODA

4-7. jun 2023. godine, KLADOVO, SRBIJA

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BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

9. simpozijum
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EnviroChem2023
sa međunarodnim učešćem

9th Symposium
Chemistry and Environmental Protection
EnviroChem2023
with international participation

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Biomass based materials for a toxic free environment

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Globally valuable resources are continuously lost through waste streams. Therein, carbon-based wastes such as biomass residues and biosolids can emit substantial amounts of greenhouse gases if landfilled or burned off. Thus, strategies to utilize these resources following concepts of circular economy are urgently needed. There is a wide pool of such resources: anaerobic digestate, manure, sewage sludge, compost, as well as biochar. These organic materials can be potentially widely used in different fields: (1) products for environmental applications; (2) organic soil amendments as source and/or a sink of nutrients, (3) for the remediation of organic and inorganic pollutants etc. Application as soil amendments is of high importance since current agricultural practices result in harmful environmental effects, including three key problems: deterioration of soil as a key non-renewable resource in our lifetime, groundwater pollution, and increasing agricultural residues [1]. It is estimated that (i) 83 % of EU arable soils, and consequently most of the groundwater is contaminated with residual pesticides at the level which put soil and ecosystem services at risk; (ii) in 65-75 % of agricultural soils, nitrogen and phosphorus cycles have exceeded their safe operating space, respectively by a factor of 3.3 and 2, resulting in diffuse pollution of terrestrial, aquatic and atmospheric ecosystems; (iii) arable soils are losing soil organic matter at a rate of 0.5 % per year which is associated with the reduction of soil fertility and productivity and an increase in greenhouse gas emissions and vulnerability against climate change [1]. These organic amendments could affect soil structure, element cycling, and nutrient composition in the soil. They can be valuable and/or a sink of nutrients. However, organic amendments often contain a range of pollutants, including heavy metals, persistent organic pollutants, potential human pathogens, and emerging pollutants such as pharmaceuticals. Additionally, the introduction of microplastics to soil, via the application of organic amendments (mainly, sewage sludge), is a topic of much relevance [2]. Therefore, development of efficient strategies to mitigate the risks associated to the application of organic amendments to soil, while benefiting from their numerous advantages is needed.

References

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